

NOTCHED RESPONSE OF NON-CRIMP FABRIC THIN-PLY LAMINATES

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1 Introduction

The use of carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP) in airframes increased drastically in the last few years. Accordingly, when promising new composite technologies appear, aircraft manufacturers try to follow up their development, aiming to improve the performance of the aircraft structures. One new technology of interest is the spread tow thin-ply technology, which is able to continuously and stably open fiber tows, and produce flat and straight plies with dry ply thicknesses as low as 0.02 mm. Widely opened tows can be cost-effectively obtained from thick tows, such as 12k filament tows or higher, without damaging the filament fibers [1]. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the pneumatic process, where the main opening takes place.

In addition to benefits regarding laminated composites design and manufacturing, such as easier homogenization, continuous lay-up, better fiber dispersion and uniformity of plies, and potential to use heavier tow yarns, thin-ply laminates also show tremendous advantages with respect to its mechanical response, namely the suppression of subcritical damage such as microcracking and delamination, extraordinary improvement of fatigue life, and increased damage tolerance. Therefore, it is not surprising to see that the interest of the scientific and industrial communities in this new technology has increased substantially in the last few years [1-16].

Fig.1. Schematic front view of the tow-spreading process with a pneumatic method (after [1]).

On the other hand, non-crimp fabrics (NCF) have been developed and proposed as reliable substitutes of both traditional unidirectional (UD) prepreg tapes and crimp textile configurations. Although slightly thicker than UD tapes, NCF are more flexible, which enables their use in liquid moulding techniques. Unlike UD tapes, the fine stitching provides the necessary rigidity to the fiber bundles, avoiding their displacement during handling of the dry reinforcement and during resin injection. In addition, this fine stitching can significantly enhance damage resistance and tolerance, as well as the through-the-thickness strength, without generating dangerous failure modes in the same extent as crimp textile reinforcements. When compared with UD prepreg laminates, only a slight reduction of the in-plane elastic and strength properties caused by the yarns is observed [17, 18].

The potential advantages of combining these two technologies – giving rise to the so-called *NCF thin-ply laminates* – are not limited to the design and manufacturing of laminated composites, but can also result in tremendous improvements of the structural integrity of composite structures such as those used in airframe construction. Therefore, the objective of this work was to study the mechanical response of this new generation of advanced composites.

2 Notched strength and size effects on NCF thin-ply laminates

An extensive experimental test program was conducted [10], including investigations on the notched strength, size effects and brittleness of NCF carbon/epoxy C-Ply™ T700/AR-2527 thin-ply laminates.

Both tensile and compressive tests were performed using two different lay-ups: a $[(0/-45)/(90/45)]_{6T}$ 24-ply thick, asymmetric lay-up, and a $[(0/-45)/(45/0)/(90/45)/(-45/90)]_S$ 16-ply thick, symmetric (by NCF bi-layer) lay-up (hereafter referred to as *lay-up 1* and *lay-up 2*, respectively). These laminates, both manufactured at VX Aerospace using vacuum bagging, included Chomarat's tow-spread C-Ply™ carbon NCF layers, with an areal weight of 150 g/m² per bi-angle layer (or 75 g/m² per ply), and Aldila's AR-2527 epoxy matrix. They both had a fiber volume fraction around 50% and a nominal ply thickness of 0.08 mm. The 0° fiber orientation is coincident with the loading direction and the ply properties were reported in [10].

The notched tests were based on specimens with central cracks and with circular holes. Particular emphasis was given to the damage mechanisms and failure modes of these materials, assessed by means of digital image correlation (DIC), which was used to monitor the onset and propagation of damage on the surface plies.

The results showed that the lay-up with blocked plies and with higher relative orientations between adjacent plies (lay-up 2) had lower unnotched strength. However, due to the larger fracture process zone observed in the notched tests (see figure 2), such lay-up had marginally higher notched strengths.

Fig.2. Surface longitudinal strain fields obtained with DIC for specimens with a 3 mm diameter hole loaded in tension (after [10]).

A size effect on the strength was observed for both the open-hole tension and compression tests. According to this experimental test program [10], the size effect and the associated notch sensitivity of ultra-thin non-crimp CFRP fabrics were similar to those observed in typical aerospace grade UD prepreg composite materials (see figure 3).

3 Bearing strength of NCF thin-ply laminates

Bolt-bearing tests were performed in [10], following the ASTM D 5961 test standard [19]. Their purpose was to evaluate the mechanical response of thin-ply laminates when subjected to local compressive efforts, typical of mechanically fastened joints.

These tests were performed in specimens with a nominal hole diameter $d = 6$ mm, end distance to hole diameter ratio $e/d = 6$, width to hole diameter ratio $W/d = 6$, and nominal length $L = 215$ mm. A bolt M6 was used with washers subjected to a torque $T = 2.2$ N m. One specimen per laminate was instrumented with one strain gage placed in the longitudinal direction away from the bearing region.

The laminate bearing stress, σ^b , is defined as [19]:

$$\sigma^b = P/(d t) \quad (1)$$

where P is the load, d is the hole diameter, and t is the nominal thickness of the specimen. The bearing strength, σ_u^b , is defined as the bearing stress at first load drop ($\sigma_u^b = \sigma^b|_{1st \text{ load drop}}$).

Fig.3. Identification of hole size effects in NCF thin-ply laminates loaded in tension, and comparison with two equivalent T800/M21 laminates (after [10]).

It was observed that the ultra-thin non-crimp CFRP fabrics exhibit an improved response to bolt-bearing loads over traditional composite materials (see figure 4). This improved response results from the ability of the NCF thin-ply laminates to block onset and propagation of damage mechanisms such as delamination, fiber kinking, matrix cracking, and through-the-thickness matrix cracking.

4 Large damage capability of NCF thin-ply laminates

As it is well known, the tensile residual strength of composite laminates in the presence of through-the-thickness notches is significantly affected by size [20]. In general, it is possible to distinguish between small-notch (i.e., “strength-dominated”) and large-notch (i.e., “toughness-dominated”) strengths.

In order to study the behavior of NCF thin-ply laminates in the presence of large through-the-thickness notches, the thin-ply NCF lay-up 2 was tested in a large damage capability (LDC) experimental study [16]. A center-notched plate, 270 mm wide (W) and 400 mm long (L), was tested in tension. The nominal length of the notch ($2a$) was 36 mm. The central notch was obtained using a milling machine, ensuring a distance of 1 mm between the notch faces. The notch tip was not sharpened, since, based on the previous work of Camanho and Catalanotti [21], no relevant difference between the fracture toughness of specimens with and without sharpened notch tips is expected.

The plate was instrumented with seven strain gages, placed in the -45° surface-ply along the longitudinal direction, as shown in figure 5. In addition, the

Fig.4. Bolt-bearing test results (after [10]).

Fig.5. Center-notched plate. Position of the strain gages ($d_1 = 11.5$ mm, $d_2 = 21.5$ mm, and $d_3 = 63.5$ mm) and DIC observation area (after [16]).

digital image correlation (DIC) technique was used to evaluate the displacement and strain fields of the 0° surface-ply, and assess damage formation and development near the notch tips. The ARAMIS DIC-2D v6.0.2 developed by GOM [22] was used. A configuration that leads to a displacement resolution in the order of 10^{-2} and a strain resolution of about 0.01-0.05% [23] was used.

Figures 6 and 7 show the results of the LDC experiments. In particular, these figures show, respectively, the surface longitudinal strain fields measured using the DIC technique for the stages corresponding to onset of crack propagation and final fracture. It can be seen that the time (proportional to the displacement)-stress relation is linear up to approximately 75% of the maximum load. The nonlinearities after 75% of the maximum

load are related with the onset of crack propagation in the notched region, as shown in figure 6. This onset of crack propagation can be identified observing the bottom right image of figure 6, where the longitudinal strain along two lines tangent to the notch tips (represented in the bottom left image) are shown. In addition to high strain concentrations at both notch tips, which can also be identified in the bottom left image, a strain discontinuity can be observed for the left notch tip, meaning that a crack extended beyond this line.

Before final fracture, and contrary to what was observed for the small notch specimens [10], the crack that propagates from the notch tips extends significantly along the notch plane, though not very regularly, as shown in figures 7 and 8. From a

macromechanical point of view, this extension occurs in discrete, finite steps, which result from a bridging process at the crack tip. This bridging process prevents crack propagation along the entire width, increasing the fracture toughness as the crack length increases, until a maximum is reached, after which final fracture occurs. Therefore, the material tested shows a crack resistance-curve (\mathcal{R} -curve). Accordingly, some small load drops can be observed after the first nonlinearity (see figures 6 and 7), corresponding to the finite crack extensions, which have some effect on the stiffness of the center-notched plate, causing the nonlinear behavior mentioned above. As it will be observed in the next sections, this bridging process and the \mathcal{R} -curve effect are fundamental in the analysis of LDC.

Fig.6. Surface longitudinal strain field, measured using the DIC technique, for the stage corresponding to onset of crack propagation in the notched region (after [16]).

Fig.7. Surface longitudinal strain field, measured using the DIC technique, showing the path of the propagating crack in the center-notched plate (after [16]).

Fig.8. Central notch region of the tested center-notched plate (after [16]).

5 Analysis methods

The presence of a hole or any other discontinuity in a composite structure introduces high local stresses that can result in subcritical damage. The analysis of failure due to cracking in composite materials resulting from stress concentrations is difficult due to material heterogeneity at the microscale (constituent scale) and at the ply scale [20].

The development of accurate, physically-based and fast strength prediction methods for composite laminates with stress concentrations is extremely important for the design of composite structures [24]. Strength prediction methods uniquely based on stress- or strain-based failure criteria are unable to predict the size effects observed in notched specimens, resulting in the same strength prediction for different hole diameters when the width to hole diameter ratio is held constant, contradicting the experimental observations [25]. Alternative methods such as the advanced numerical models available for the strength prediction of composite laminates require non-linear solvers, resulting in long computing times that are unacceptable for preliminary sizing and for optimization of composite structures [24]. To satisfactorily combine accuracy and speed, design tools based on closed-form solutions have been developed. Such tools are based on models such as the inherent flaw model (IFM) [26], the point-stress (PS) and average-stress (AS) models [27], or the recently proposed Finite Fracture Mechanics (FFMs) model [24].

The analysis methods should also be able to capture and predict the distinct “strength-dominated” and “toughness-dominated” material behaviors. In addition, they should be able to provide failure predictions beyond the notch sizes and structural geometries tested during material characterization, and the number of material properties required for the analysis models should be minimized to reduce the material testing requirements [20]. To ensure this extrapolation capability, suitable models must be based on the actual physics of the problem.

The existing analytical models, such as the IFM [26], and PS and AS models [27], use empirical characteristic distances that, in practice, are determined from notched strength data. They are

often thought as correction factors that account for apparent changes in the stress intensity with increasing crack size, with limited physical meaning. Although analysis models that include characteristic distances are better at predicting small crack experimental trends than, for example, LEFM models, both fail to predict LDC, typically yielding conservative estimates [20].

An alternative approach is the Mar-Lin model [28]. This model captures the reduced sensitivity of composite materials to large changes in notch size by allowing the singularity, n , to be other than the square-root (as in LEFM). This model was successfully used to predict LDC from smaller notch data, avoiding excessive conservatism. However, the exponent n is an additional empirical parameter that also needs to be experimentally determined (typically by curve-fitting). In addition, a precise, verified method for determining the appropriate singularity value in the absence of large notch data has not been developed. In fact, caution should be exercised in selecting exponents for extrapolation, since it is possible to select values that over-predict LDC (unconservative results). Because, in general, verification tests or LDC test data are required [20], the Mar-Lin model [28] is not addressed in this work.

The FFMs model, recently proposed by Camanho et al. [24], results in improvements over the traditional strength prediction methods [24, 29]. This model assumes that crack propagation occurs when a stress-based criterion, similar to Whitney and Nuismer's AS model [27], and an energy-based criterion are simultaneously satisfied, and considers that failure occurs by the propagation of kinematically admissible cracks with finite sizes. Assuming that the propagation of the macrocrack that leads to final failure occurs along the x -direction, and for the particular case of a specimen with an uncracked central circular hole of radius R , fracture occurs when the following system of equations is satisfied [24]:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{1}{l} \int_R^{R+l} \sigma_{yy}(x, 0) dx = X^L \\ \frac{1}{l} \int_R^{R+l} \mathcal{K}_I^2(a) da = \mathcal{K}_{Ic}^2 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma_{yy}(x,0)$ is the stress distribution along the x -axis, X^L is the laminate unnotched strength, $\mathcal{K}_I(a)$ is the stress intensity factor (SIF) for a plate with two symmetric cracks emanating from a central circular hole, \mathcal{K}_{Ic} is the mode I laminate fracture toughness, and l is the crack extension at failure.

A comparison between the predictions of the PS, AS and FFMs models and the open-hole tests results obtained using the NCF thin-ply laminates are shown in figures 9 and 10 for tension and compression, respectively. The test results obtained in the experimental program [10] for the open-hole tension specimens with a 6 mm diameter hole and for the open-hole compression specimens with a 5 mm diameter hole were used to calibrate the PS and AS models and calculate the corresponding

(a) Lay-up 1

(b) Lay-up 2

Fig.9. Predictions and experimental results for the open-hole NCF thin-ply laminates loaded in tension (after [15]). The relative errors of the FFMs predictions are also shown.

(a) Lay-up 1

(b) Lay-up 2

Fig.10. Predictions and experimental results for the open-hole NCF thin-ply laminates loaded in compression (after [15]). The relative errors of the FFMs predictions are also shown.

characteristic distances (r_{ot}). The tensile and compressive fracture toughness required in the FFMs model were reported in [10].

Comparing the predictions of the notched response in tension with the experimental results, errors below 14% were found for the different methods [15]. As it would be expected, the predictions obtained using the AS model are more accurate than those obtained with the PS model; however, the FFMs model provides the most accurate predictions.

For the notched response in compression, figure 10, and comparing the predictions with the experimental results, errors below 10% were found for the different models [15]. In this case, the predictions of the FFMs model were not as accurate as the predictions of the alternative models. However, it

should be noted that, unlike the alternative models, which use an inverse calibration from one of the open-hole compression tests, resulting in good predictions for hole diameters around that used for calibration ($d = 5$ mm), the FFMs model, besides the laminate compressive unnotched strength, simply requires the laminate compressive fracture toughness, which is an independently measured material property. Yet the errors are still very reasonable, in the same range of those obtained for the tensile notched strength (compare figures 9 and 10).

In order to more accurately predict LDC from small notch data, the effect of the \mathcal{R} -curve has to be taken into account in the analysis models, otherwise conservative predictions are systematically obtained – see figure 11 (though very good predictions are found for the stress at first crack propagation).

The effect of the \mathcal{R} -curve in determining the crack length corresponding to unstable crack propagation of a center-notched laminate can be taken into account using the FFMs model by rewriting the system of equations (2) as:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{1}{l} \int_a^{a+l} \sigma_{yy}(x, 0) dx = X_T^L \\ \int_a^{a+l} \mathcal{G}_I(a) da = \int_0^l \mathcal{R}(\Delta a) d\Delta a \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Fig.11. Predictions and experimental results for the tensile residual strength of the NCF thin-ply lay-up 2 (after [16]). The relative errors of the FFMs predictions with respect to the experimentally obtained ultimate strength ($\epsilon_r = -21.8\%$) and stress at first propagation ($\epsilon_r = 0.7\%$) are also shown. Note that the small notch experimental data was used to calibrate the analysis models (yielding no errors for such geometry).

where $\mathcal{G}_I(a)$ is the energy release rate (ERR) and $\mathcal{R}(\Delta a)$ is the \mathcal{R} -curve, expressed in terms of a critical ERR, of the laminate. Catalanotti et al. [30] measured the \mathcal{R} -curve of the NCF thin-ply lay-up 2 using a methodology based on Bažant's size effect law [31]. A length of the fracture process zone $l_{fpz} = 1.92$ mm and a fracture toughness at propagation $\mathcal{R}_{SS} = 101.5$ kJ/m² were reported.

Figure 12 shows the predictions of the tensile residual strength of a center-notched thin-ply NCF plate for a wide range of crack lengths ($2a$), obtained using the FFMs models without and taking into account the \mathcal{R} -curve of the laminate. Figure 12 also shows the experimental results for the center-notched specimen ($2a = 4$ mm) [10] and for the center-notched plate ($2a = 36$ mm) [16], and the corresponding relative errors.

Observing the results shown in figure 12, it is clear that the introduction of the \mathcal{R} -curve in the FFMs formulation results in a significant improvement of the predictions of LDC. Using the traditional analysis methods, the relative errors of the predictions range from -41.2% to -21.6% for a center-notched plate with a crack length $2a = 36$ mm [16], whereas the FFMs prediction that takes into

Fig.12. Predictions and experimental results for the tensile residual strength of the NCF thin-ply lay-up 2 (after [16]). The relative errors of the predictions of the FFMs model that take into account the \mathcal{R} -curve of the laminate, with respect to the experimentally obtained ultimate strengths (for both small and large notches), are also shown. Note that the small notch experimental data was used to calculate the fracture toughness used in the FFMs model that does not take into account the \mathcal{R} -curve of the laminate (yielding no errors for this geometry).

account the \mathcal{R} -curve of the laminate has a relative error of -9.7%, which is within the range typically obtained by the traditional analysis methods for small damage coupons [15, 24, 29].

6 Conclusions

The results presented in this work show that the thin-ply laminates have great potential, discarding any evidence of inherent brittleness in both tension and compression. It also showed that changing the stacking sequence, i.e. maximizing the relative ply orientations between adjacent plies and "blocking" plies with the same fiber orientation, the notch sensitivity of the thin-ply and standard laminates decreases in both tension and compression. However, with thin-ply laminates, this is achieved reducing to a minimum the development of subcritical damage such as delamination and transverse cracking, in tension, and fiber kinking, in compression.

This work demonstrates that application of NCF thin-ply laminates in primary structures can clearly result in structural integrity improvements, without degrading the notched response of the composite structures. Such improvements include (i) suppression of subcritical damage such as delamination and transverse cracking, particularly important in applications subjected to mechanical fatigue and load reversals, and (ii) optimized behavior in mechanically fastened joints, due to the superior performance of these laminates when subjected to bearing loads.

Regarding the LDC of the NCF thin-ply laminates, a linear displacement-stress relation was observed up to approximately 75% of the maximum load. Small load drops were observed, corresponding to finite crack extensions, which had some effect on the stiffness of the center-notched plate, causing the nonlinear behavior observed above 75% of the maximum load. Extensive crack propagation occurred before final fracture. From a macromechanical point of view, this extension took place in discrete, finite steps, which resulted from a bridging process at the crack tip. This bridging process blocked crack propagation along the entire width, increasing fracture toughness as the crack length increased, until a maximum was reached,

after which final fracture occurred – \mathcal{R} -curve effect. Near the notch tips, some fiber splitting was observed in both 0° and -45° surface-ply, as well as some separated plies due to delamination, which occurred after unstable crack propagation. Still, the extent of such damage mechanisms was reduced.

Based on a new test methodology [30], which is able to characterize the \mathcal{R} -curve of (thin) laminated composites that show improved resistance to crack propagation, such as the NCF thin-ply laminates studied in the present work, an analytical formula for the \mathcal{R} -curve can be obtained. This formula was used in the FFMs model to take into account the \mathcal{R} -curve of the material. It was observed that the introduction of the \mathcal{R} -curve in the FFMs formulation clearly has a significant positive effect in the predictions of LDC. More reliable analyses of large through-penetration damage of composites can be obtained without fitting parameters or complex finite element analyses. The analytical FFMs model can be used in preliminary design and implemented in optimization codes, without requiring verification tests or fine tuning parameters that account for scale modifications. Furthermore, because it is physically-based, only independently measured material properties are necessary (the laminate strength and the \mathcal{R} -curve), which can be easily included in the experimental characterization programs that are often carried out in the composites industry.

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References

- [1] S. Sihh, R.Y. Kim, K. Kawabe, S.W. Tsai. "Experimental studies of thin-ply laminated composites". *Compos Sci Technol*, Vol. 67, pp 996-1008, 2007.
- [2] Y. Nishikawa, K. Okubo, T. Fujii, K. Kawabe. "Fatigue crack constraint in plain-woven CFRP using newly-developed spread tows". *Int J Fatigue* Vol. 28, pp 1248-1253, 2006.
- [3] K. Kawabe, H. Sasayama, K. Kageyama, N. Ogata. "Effect of ply thickness on compressive properties in multidirectionally laminated composites". *J Jpn Soc Compos Mater* Vol. 34, pp 173-181, 2008 (in Japanese).
- [4] T. Yokozeki, Y. Aoki, T. Ogasawara. "Experimental characterization of strength and damage resistance properties of thin-ply carbon fiber/toughened epoxy laminates". *Compos Struct* Vol. 82, pp 382-389, 2008.
- [5] T. Yokozeki, A. Kuroda, A. Yoshimura, T. Ogasawara, T. Aoki. "Damage characterization in thin-ply composite laminates under out-of-plane transverse loading". *Compos Struct* Vol. 93, pp 49-57, 2010.
- [6] H. Takeuchi, H. Saito, I. Kimpara. "Restraining effects of transverse cracking in 90° layer of thin-ply CFRP cross-ply laminates". In: *Proceedings of ACCM-7*. Taipei, November, 2010.
- [7] J. Moon, M. Kim, C. Kim, S. Bhowmik. "Improvement of tensile properties of CFRP composites under LEO space environment by applying MWNTs and thin-ply". *Compos Part A-Appl S* Vol. 42, pp 694-701, 2011.
- [8] H. Saito, M. Morita, K. Kawabe, M. Kanasaki, H. Takeuchi, M. Tanaka, I. Kimpara I. "Effect of ply-thickness on impact damage morphology in CFRP laminates". *J Reinf Plast Comp* Vol. 30, pp 1097-1106, 2011.
- [9] H. Saito, H. Takeuchi, I. Kimpara. "Experimental evaluation of the damage growth restraining in 90° layer of thin-ply CFRP cross-ply laminates". *Adv Compos Mater* Vol. 21, pp 57-66, 2012.
- [10] A. Arteiro, G. Catalanotti, J. Xavier, P.P. Camanho. "Notched response of non-crimp fabric thin-ply laminates". *Compos Sci Technol* Vol. 79, pp 97-114, 2013.
- [11] P. Linde, N. Heltsch, T. Kruse, S. Das, C. Vernier. "Second generation composites". In: *Proceedings of the 19. Nationales Symposium – SAMPE Deutschland e.V.* Hamburg, February, 2013 (in German).
- [12] P.P. Camanho, A. Arteiro, G. Catalanotti, A.R. Melro. "Mechanics of ultra-thin ply laminates". In: *Proceedings of CompTest-2013*. Aalborg, April, pp 3, 2013.
- [13] R. Amacher, J. Cugnoni, J. Botsis. "Experimental characterization and modeling of thin ply-size effect". In: *Proceedings of CompTest-2013*. Aalborg, April, pp 33-34, 2013.
- [14] A. Kuraishi, T. Itoh, J. Kimoto, S. Ochi, N. Hirano. "Applicability of C-ply Bi-angle™ NCF to aircraft parts". In: *Proceedings of ICCM19*. Montréal, July, 2013.
- [15] A. Arteiro, G. Catalanotti, J. Xavier, P.P. Camanho. "Notched response of non-crimp fabric thin-ply laminates: analysis methods". Submitted for publication to *Compos Sci Technol*.
- [16] A. Arteiro, G. Catalanotti, J. Xavier, P.P. Camanho. "Large damage capability of non-crimp fabric thin-ply laminates". Submitted for publication to *Compos Part A-Appl S*.
- [17] N. Tessitore, A. Riccio. "A novel FEM model for biaxial non-crimp fabric composite materials under tension". *Comput Struct*, Vol. 84, pp 1200-1207, 2006.
- [18] A. Petriccione, D. Annicchiarico, V. Antonucci, M. Giordano, A. Riccio, F. Scaramuzzino. "A stiffness volume averaging based approach to model non-crimp fabric reinforced composites". *Compos Sci Technol*, Vol. 72, pp 360-369, 2012.
- [19] "Standard test method for bearing response of polymer matrix composite laminates". *ASTM D 5961/D 5961M-01*. American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM), West Conshohocken, PA, USA.
- [20] MIL-HDBK-17-3F, "Composite Materials Handbook". Vol. 3 of 5: *Polymer Matrix Composites Materials Usage, Design and Analysis*. Department of Defense Handbook, June, 2002.
- [21] P.P. Camanho, G. Catalanotti. "On the relation between the mode I fracture toughness of a composite laminate and that of a 0° ply: Analytical model and experimental validation". *Eng Fract Mech* Vol. 78, pp 2535-2546, 2011.
- [22] *GOM International AG*. Bremsgarterstrasse 89B, CH-8967 Widén, Switzerland.
- [23] J. Xavier, A.M.P. de Jesus, J.J.L. Morais, J.M.T. Pinto. "Stereovision measurements on evaluating the modulus of elasticity of wood by compression tests parallel to the grain". *Constr Build Mater* Vol. 26(1), pp 207-215, 2012.
- [24] P.P. Camanho, G.H. Erçin, G. Catalanotti, S. Mahdi, P. Linde. "A finite fracture mechanics model for the prediction of the open-hole strength of composite laminates". *Compos Part A-Appl S* Vol. 43, pp 1219-1225, 2012.

- [25] P.P. Camanho, P. Maimí, C.G. Dávila. "Prediction of size effects in notched laminates using continuum damage mechanics". *Compos Sci Technol* Vol. 67, pp 2715-2727, 2007.
- [26] M.E. Waddoups, J.R. Eisenmann, B.E. Kaminski. "Macroscopic fracture mechanics of advanced composite materials". *J Compos Mater* Vol. 5, pp 446-454, 1971.
- [27] J.M. Whitney, R.J. Nuismer. "Stress fracture criteria for laminated composites containing stress concentrations". *J Compos Mater* Vol. 8, pp 253-265, 1974.
- [28] J.W. Mar, K.Y. Lin. "Fracture mechanics correlation for tensile failure of filamentary composites with holes". *J Aircraft* Vol. 14, pp 703-704, 1977.
- [29] G.H. Erçin, P.P. Camanho, J. Xavier, G. Catalanotti, S. Mahdi, P. Linde. "Size effects on the tensile and compressive failure of notched composite laminates". *Compos Struct* Vol. 96, pp 736-744, 2013.
- [30] G. Catalanotti, A. Arteiro, M. Hayati, P.P. Camanho. "Intralaminar tensile fracture toughness and crack resistance curves of polymer composites". Submitted for publication to *Eng Fract Mech*.
- [31] Z.P. Bažant, J. Planas. "*Fracture and Size Effect in Concrete and Other Quasibrittle Materials*". CRC Press LLC, 1997.